

New records of arboreal beetles (Insecta: Coleoptera) from Bulgaria

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Abstract: Fifteen arboreal species of the families Ptinidae (1), Latridiidae (1), Trogossitidae (1), Mycetophagidae (1), Tenebrionidae (3), Zopheridae (3) and Laemophloeidae (5) are recorded from Bulgaria. One species (*Ptinomorphus imperialis*) is saproxilic, 11 species (*Melanophthalma fuscipennis*, *Litargus connexus*, *Tribolium castaneum*, imago of *Colobicus hirtus*, *Synchita separanda*, *S. undata*, *Cryptolestes ferrugineus*, *C. pusilloides*, *Laemophloeus monilis*, *Leptophloeus alternans* and *Placonotus testaceus*) are mycophagous, and four species (*Nemozoma elongatum*, *Corticus linearis*, *C. pini* and larvae of *Colobicus hirtus*) are predatory. The first detailed records for *Synchita separanda* and *S. undata* from Bulgaria are given. Thus both species are confirmed for the country, having been omitted in the Palearctic Catalog of Coleoptera. Five species, *Melanophthalma fuscipennis*, *Corticus pini*, *Cryptolestes pusilloides*, *Laemophloeus monilis* and *L. alternans* are reported for the second time from Bulgaria. Other three species, *Ptinomorphus imperialis*, *Nemozoma elongatum* and *Placonotus testaceus* are cited for the third time from the country. *Pityokteines curvidens* was found as a new prey for *Nemozoma elongatum*, *Corticus linearis* and *C. pini*.

Keywords: forest trees, mycophages, predators, prey, rare beetles, saproxilic species, South Dobrudzha

Introduction

The diversity of the beetles (Coleoptera) in Bulgaria is still far from well-known. Hubenov (2008) stated that approximately 6000 species are known which is at about two thirds of the expected species composition. This estimate of species is certainly slightly lower than that currently known; however, fixing the actual number of reported beetle species in the country remains difficult and it is not the aim of present report. Traditionally, families of Cucujiformia contain-

ing species with cryptic habits (living in fungi, leaf litter, dead wood or under tree bark) have remained out of research interest by the national entomologists. Examples of still little investigated groups in Bulgaria, which known faunal composition vary between 30% and 70%, are Ciidae, Corylophidae, Cryptophagidae, Laemophloeidae, Latridiidae, Melandryidae, Monotomidae, Phalacridae, Zopheridae.

Over the last decade, intensive processes of tree drying have been observed in coniferous plantations in the lower and middle forest vegetation belts in

Table 1. Main characteristics of the studied areas.

N	Locality	Geographical coordinates	Altitude, m a.s.l.	Tree species	Stand type	Age, years	Sample collection, date, collector
1	Petrich	N41.38729° E23.20209°	305	<i>Pseudotsuga menziesii</i>	Plantation	51	27.09.2024, G. Georgiev
2	Sofia	N42.62032° E23.38379°	647	<i>Abies alba</i>	Ornamentals	65	11.07.2024, M. Yanev
3	Trigortsi Village 1	N43.52235° E28.18793°	200	<i>Acer platanoides</i>	Forest belt	38	24.10–26.11.2024, V. Ivanov
4	Trigortsi Village 2	N43.50353° E28.15319°	210	<i>Tilia platyphyllos</i>	Forest belt	33	31.07–24.10.2024, V. Ivanov
5	Trigortsi Village 3	N43.50353° E28.15319°	210	<i>Fraxinus ornus</i>	Forest belt	33	31.07.2024, V. Ivanov
6	Dropla Village	N43.57271° E28.08079°	215	<i>Acer campestre</i>	Forest belt	48	24.10.2024, V. Ivanov
7	Petleshkovo Village	N43.65243° E28.01882°	831	<i>Gleditsia triacanthos</i>	Forest belt	40	17.04.2025, V. Ivanov

Bulgaria (Mirchev et al., 2016) and in the field protective forest belts in Southern Dobrudzha (Dodev et al., 2023; Georgieva et al., 2024a, b). The drying is associated with the physiological weakening of tree vegetation due to deterioration of ecological conditions – uneven distribution of precipitation, prolonged periods of drought, heat waves, etc. (Georgieva et al., 2024a). The presence of numerous drying and dead trees creates favorable conditions for enriching entomological diversity in forest ecosystems.

The present study reports rare and interesting saproxilic, mycophagous and predatory arboreal beetles in Bulgaria.

Material and methods

The studies were conducted in 2024 and 2025 on seven tree species in field protective forest belts, forest plantations and ornamentals in Bulgaria (Table 1).

Cuttings of stems of approximate length 25–30 cm were collected from drying trees. The samples were transported to the Forest Research Institute in Sofia where the cuttings were kept at room temperature (18–22 °C) in plastic boxes. They were observed weekly for appearance of insects.

The emerged beetles were stored in ethanol. The identifications of species were made using by the

illustrated online keys of the Arved Lompe (www.coleo-net.de/coleo/index.htm .

The biological material was deposited in the entomological collections of Forest Research Institute at Bulgarian Academy of Sciences and the National Museum of Natural History in Sofia at Bulgarian Academy of Sciences.

Results

In this study, 15 species from 7 coleopteran families were established in Bulgaria.

Order Coleoptera Linnaeus, 1758
Suborder Polyphaga Emery, 1886
Superfamily Bostrichoidea Latreille, 1802
Family Ptinidae Latreille, 1802

Ptinomorphus imperialis (Linnaeus, 1767). Material examined: 1 ex., Petleshkovo (loc. N 7), found under bark 01.12.2024.

Superfamily Coccinelloidea Latreille, 1807
Family Latridiidae Erichson, 1842

Melanophthalma (*Cortilena*) *fuscipennis* (Mannerheim, 1844) (Fig. 1A). Material examined: 1

Fig. 1. Reared beetles: A – *Melanophthalma fuscipennis*; B – *Corticeus linearis*; C – *Corticeus pini*; D – *Synchita separanda*; E – *Synchita undata*; F – *Cryptolestes pusilloides*; G – *Laemophloeus monilis*; H – *Leptophloeus alternans*.

ex., Trigortsi 2 (loc. N 4), emergence 14.10–22.11.2024.

Superfamily Cleroidea Latreille, 1802
Family Trogossitidae Latreille, 1802

Nemozoma elongatum (Linnaeus, 1761). Material examined: 2 exx., Sofia (loc. N 2), emergence 01.12.2024. Reared from galleries of *Pityokteines curvidens* (Germar, 1823) (Coleoptera: Curculionidae, Scolytinae) along with many adults of the bark beetle.

Superfamily Tenebrionoidea Latreille, 1802
Family Mycetophagidae Leach, 1815

Litargus (Litargus) connexus (Geoffroy, 1785). Material examined: 3 exx., Trigortsi 2 (loc. N 4), emergence 14.10–22.11.2024.

Family Tenebrionidae Latreille, 1802

Corticeus (Corticeus) linearis (Fabricius, 1790) (Fig. 1B). Material examined: 5 exx., Sofia (loc. N 2), emergence 01.12.2024. Reared from galleries of

P. curvidens along with many adults of the bark beetle.

Corticeus (*Corticeus*) *pini* (Panzer, 1799) (Fig. 1C). Material examined: 8 exx., Sofia (loc. N 2), emergence 01.12.2024. Reared from galleries of *P. curvidens* along with many adults of the bark beetle.

Tribolium castaneum (Herbst, 1797). Material examined: 1 ex., Trigortsi 3 (loc. N 5), emergence 01.12.2024.

Family Zopheridae Solier, 1834

Colobicus hirtus (Rossi, 1790). Material examined: 1 ex., Trigortsi 2 (loc. N 4), emergence 14.10–22.11.2024; 2 exx., Dropla (loc. N 6), emergence 22.11.2024.

Synchita separanda (Reitter, 1882) (Fig. 1D). Material examined: 1 ex., Trigortsi 2 (loc. N 4), emergence 14.10–22.11.2024.

Synchita undata Guérin-Méneville, 1844 (Fig. 1E). Material examined: 2 exx., Petrich (loc. N 1), found under bark 27.09.2024; 2 exx., Trigortsi 1 (loc. N 3), emergence 29.10.–01.12.2024.

Superfamily Cucujoidea Latreille, 1802

Family Laemophloeidae Ganglbauer, 1899

Cryptolestes ferrugineus (Stephens, 1831). Material examined: 1 ex., Petrich (loc. N 1), found under bark 27.09.2024; 1 ex., Trigortsi 2 (loc. N 4), emergence 01.12.2024.

Cryptolestes pussiloides (Steel & Howe, 1952) (Fig. 1F). Material examined: 2 exx., Petrich (loc. N 1), found under bark 27.09.2024.

Laemophloeus monilis (Fabricius, 1787) (Fig. 1G). Material examined: 1 ex., Trigortsi 2 (loc. N 4), emergence 22.11.2024.

Leptophloeus alternans (Erichson, 1846) (Fig. 1E). Material examined: 7 exx., Sofia (loc. N 2), emergence 01.12.2024.

Placonotus testaceus (Fabricius, 1787). Material examined: 2 exx., Trigortsi 2 (loc. N 4), emergence 14.10–22.11.2024.

The majority of records concern rare or poorly studied dendrophilous beetles. In this study, the first specified localities for *Synchita separanda* and *S. undata* in Bulgaria are given. Five species

(*Melanophthalma fuscipennis*, *Corticeus pini*, *Cryptolestes pussiloides*, *Laemophloeus monilis* and *L. alternans*) are reported for the second time from Bulgaria, and three ones (*Ptinomorphus imperialis*, *Nemozoma elongatum* and *Placonotus testaceus*) – for the third time from the country.

In trophic aspect, one species (*Ptinomorphus imperialis*) is saproxilic, 11 species (*Melanophthalma fuscipennis*, *Litargus connexus*, *Tribolium castaneum*, imago of *Colobicus hirtus*, *Synchita separanda*, *S. undata*, *Cryptolestes ferrugineus*, *C. pussiloides*, *Laemophloeus monilis*, *Leptophloeus alternans* and *Placonotus testaceus*) are mycophagous, and four species (*Nemozoma elongatum*, *Corticeus linearis*, *C. pini* and larvae of *Colobicus hirtus*) are predatory. The fir engraver beetle, *Pityokteines curvidens* was found as a new prey for *Nemozoma elongatum*, *Corticeus linearis* and *C. pini*.

Discussion

Ptinomorphus imperialis was so far recorded for Bulgaria by Horion (1961, sub *Hedobia imperialis*) and Angelov (1968, sub *H. imperialis*). The new record near Petleshkovo Village appears the third country record.

Melanophthalma fuscipennis is one of the two Bulgarian species known from subgenus *Cortilena* Motschulsky, 1867. The species was first published for the country by Reike (2018). The finding near Trigortsi Village comes out the second record for *M. fuscipennis* from the country.

Nemozoma elongatum is a predacious species on bark insects (mainly bark beetles). It was recorded twice from the country (Markovich, 1909; Guéorguiev et al., 2003). The species occurrence near Sofia reflects its third announcement from Bulgaria. *Nemozoma elongatum* is mainly associated with *Ips typographus* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Pityogenes chalcographus* (Linnaeus, 1760) and *Taphrorychus bicolor* (Herbst, 1793) (Kenis et al., 2004). Therefore, the established in this study *Pityokteines curvidens* is a new prey for the predator.

Litargus connexus was recently been catalogued among the rest species of the family (Guéorguiev et al., 2023). It seems not to be so rare species in the country rather than a rarely collected and identified.

Examining literature sources for darkling beetles, in terms of data for Bulgaria, Sivilov

(2015) notes that six species of the genus *Corticus* Piller & Mitterpacher, 1783 were reported for the country, *C. bicolor* (G.-A. Olivier, 1790), *C. fasciatus* (Fabricius, 1790), *C. fraxini* (Kugelann, 1794), *C. linearis*, *C. longulus* (Gyllenhal, 1827) and *C. unicolor* Piller & Mitterpacher, 1783. Among them, only *C. bicolor*, *C. fraxini* and *C. unicolor* are indicated for the country in the catalogue of the Palaearctic Tenebrionidae (Löbl et al., 2008; Iwan et al., 2020), and the remaining three are left unmentioned. However, in the Fauna Europaea database, a specimen of *C. pini* has been collected in 1998 in Nessebar region in Bulgaria (Finnish Museum of Natural History – Zoology Unit, 2025). Worth noting that *C. linearis* and *C. pini* are considered as predators of concrete species of bark beetles by Sarikaya & Avci (2009). In this study, *C. linearis* and *C. pini* were reared for first time from *Abies alba* Mill. attacked by *Pityokteines curvidens*. Soldati & Soldati (2010) stated that in France preferable hosts of *Corticus pini* are the bark beetles *Hylurgus ligniperda* (Fabricius, 1787), *Orthotomicus erosus* (Wollaston, 1854), *Ips sexdentatus* (Börner, 1776) and *Ips typographus* (Linnaeus, 1758), and of *C. linearis* – *Ips acuminatus* (Gyllenhal, 1827), *Pityogenes bidentatus* (Herbst, 1784), *Cryphalus piceae* (Ratzeburg, 1837), *Pityophthorus pityographus* (Ratzeburg, 1837), *Tomicus destruens* (Wollaston, 1865) and *Orthotomicus erosus*.

According to Sivilov (2015) *Tribolium castaneum* is a species frequently observed and widely distributed in Bulgaria. As reported by the same author (ibid.) it has not been discovered in natural conditions. The sole specimen from Trigortsi Village was reared from stem samples of *Fraxinus ornus*. Therefore, this data represent first finding of *T. castaneum* in a natural habitat in the country.

Burakowski et al. (1986) stated that *Colobicus hirtus* is a relict of primeval forests (see also Temreshev, 2025). In Poland the species is rather rare and recently was found in a forest patch with old, 165-year-old beeches (Ruta, 2020). For the first time in Bulgaria, *C. hirtus* was recorded by Anonymous (1907, sub *C. emarginatus* Erichson) before more than a century. After that, the species was cited by Palm (1966, sub *C. marginatus* Latreille) from the vicinities of town of Nessebar and quite recently by Bencheva & Doychev (2022) from the State Forest

Enterprise ‘Strumyani’ in Southwestern Bulgaria. Palm (ibid.) mentioned that he observed the species under spongy bark of a stump of *Juglans* whereas the latter authors did rear it from parts of dead standing stem of *Quercus suber* L.

Synchita separanda and *S. undata* have been noted for Bulgaria in the catalogue of Palaearctic Zopheridae (Ślipiński & Schuh, 2008; Schuh, 2020). Survey of literature sources about this family, including the revision of the “*variegata*” species group of *Synchita* Hellwig, 1792 (Schuh, 1998), did not revealed data for country presence of any of the two species. This means that the indications of *S. separanda* and *S. undata* for the Bulgarian fauna are probably due to unpublished materials in entomological collections. For example, a specimen of *S. separanda* from Bulgaria (without specified locality) is preserved in the Lund University Biological Museum (Fägerström, 2025). Consequently, the notifications given in current study represent the first detailed records of their occurrence in Bulgaria.

Cryptolestes ferrugineus is a common species in the country that has been reported as pest on grain cultures (Buresch & Lazarov, 1956, sub *Laemophloeus ferrugineus*). The other herein treated member of the genus, *Cryptolestes pussiloides* was first indicated for Bulgaria by Obretenchev (2013) as sample isolated from wheat grain. The record about the latter above the town of Petrich appears the second country record and the first country finding in a natural habitat. Other two species of Laemophloeidae also were reported for Bulgaria once only each of them, *Laemophloeus monilis* (Markovich, 1909) and *Leptophloeus alternans* (Chorbadzhev, 1930). The former was mentioned under the bark of rotting oak trees whereas the latter – from galleries of the bark beetle *Scolytus rugulosus* (Müller, 1818). Last treated herein representative of the family, *Placonotus testaceus* was noted twice for the country, respectively by Obretenchev (2013, sub *Laemophloeus testaceus*) and Guéorguiev & Ljubomirov (2009). Worth noting that the five species were left unmentioned for Bulgaria in the catalogue of the Palaearctic Laemophloeidae (Wegrzynowicz, 2007). That is why, we treat the notifications herein included for *Cryptolestes pussiloides*, *Laemophloeus monilis* and *L. alternans* as their second records from Bulgaria while that for *Placonotus testaceus* – as its third finding from the country.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the new information expands knowledge about the distribution and ecology of rare and poorly studied arboreal beetles in Bulgaria.

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Conflicts of interest

No potential conflict of interest has been reported by the authors, reviewers, or subject editor.

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